

ENHANCING JOB INVOLVEMENT THROUGH SUPERVISORY SUPPORT AND ORGANISATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR AMONG FEDERAL WORKERS IN UYO

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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of supervisory support and organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) on job involvement among federal government workers in Uyo, Nigeria. It employed a cross-sectional design to collect data from 367 participants selected through convenient and purposive sampling. Of these participants, 253 (68.9%) were males and 114 (31.1%) were females, with ages ranging from 23 to 61 years (mean = 40.5, SD = 8.5). Data were gathered using two instruments: the Organisational Citizenship Behaviour Scale and the Supervisory Support Scale. The study tested two hypotheses using hierarchical regression analysis at an alpha level of 0.05. Utilising a quantitative approach, data were collected from federal employees in Uyo through structured questionnaires. The findings reveal a significant positive relationship between supervisory support and job involvement in the first hypothesis, highlighting that employees who perceive high levels of support from their supervisors are more likely to be deeply engaged in their work ($\beta = .32$; $t = 5.25$; $p < 0.05$). The second hypothesis indicated that organisational citizenship behaviour significantly predicted job involvement ($\beta = -.13$; $t = -2.10$; $p < 0.05$). The results offer valuable insights for policymakers and organisational leaders in Uyo, advocating for practices that bolster supervisory support and promote organisational citizenship as strategies to boost job involvement and overall employee performance. The study recommends, among other things, that workers should be recognised, valued, treated with care, and not subjected to discrimination in the workplace.

Keywords: Supervisory Support, Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (Ocb), Job Involvement, Workplace Discrimination

INTRODUCTION

Job involvement is critical for employee motivation and organisational performance, as it reflects the extent to which job satisfaction is integral to an individual's identity and well-being (Lawler & Hall, 1970). While high job involvement motivates employees to excel, leading to increased productivity and commitment, low involvement results in apathy and poor performance (Iroegbu, 2012; Ogunyemi et al., 2018). This concept is essential across various sectors, including civil service, where productivity has declined due to insufficient supervisory support, lack of organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB), and perceived injustice (Okechukwu, 2017; Ogunyemi et al., 2018).

Organisational justice plays a significant role in job involvement, with distributive justice—fair reward distribution—being key to fostering positive behaviours like OCB and job satisfaction (Mishra et al., 2015; Adzie, 2016). Employees treated fairly are more likely to demonstrate higher involvement and contribute to organisational success (Eder & Eisenberger, 2015). However, in Nigeria, workplace injustice remains prevalent, leading to absenteeism, strikes, and decreased engagement (Efanga & Akpan, 2015).

Research shows that job involvement is linked to reduced absenteeism, lower turnover intentions, and better performance (Tian et al., 2019). This study seeks to explore the impact of organisational justice, OCB, and supervisory support on job involvement among federal workers in Uyo, aiming to provide strategies for improving engagement in Nigeria's public sector.

Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives guiding the study are:

- i. To examine if organisational citizenship behaviour will significantly predict the job involvement of employees in the federal civil service in Akwa Ibom State;
- ii. To examine if supervisory support will significantly predict the job involvement of employees in the federal civil service in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

The study shall answer the following questions:

- i. Will organisational citizenship behaviour significantly predict job involvement of federal workers such that workers with high organisational citizenship behaviour will lead to high job involvement among the Federal employees in Akwa Ibom State?
- ii. Will supervisory support significantly predict job involvement of federal workers such that workers with high organisational justice will lead to high job involvement among the federal employees in Akwa Ibom State?

Research Hypotheses

In line with the outlined research questions, this study proposes the following hypotheses:

- i. Organisational citizenship behaviour will significantly predict job involvement of employees in the federal civil service in Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. Supervisory support will significantly predict job involvement of employees in the federal civil service in Akwa Ibom State.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study was hinged on the theories below:

Transformational Leadership Theory

Transformational leadership theory, originally proposed by Downton in 1973 and expanded by Burns in 1978, suggests that employees become more engaged in their work when led by transformational leaders. This approach encourages leaders to exhibit authentic and strong leadership, with the expectation that employees in Nigeria, as well as elsewhere, will be motivated to work with passion and enhance organisational productivity.

Social Exchange Theory Homans (1964)

Social exchange theory suggests that the relationship between supervisory support and employees' intention to leave is influenced by both extrinsic and intrinsic rewards. Extrinsic rewards, such as payment and employment benefits (Blau, 1964), and intrinsic rewards, such as self-esteem and social-emotional support (Angle and Perry, 1983), play a role in this dynamic. The theory posits that effective supervisor support is rooted in significant social bonds between supervisors and employees.

Adams' Equity Theory (1965)

Adams' equity theory, introduced by Adams in 1965, posits that employees are motivated when they perceive they are receiving fair rewards for their work. This theory explains employee behaviour and motivation by suggesting that employees compare their own inputs (such as effort and skills) and outputs (such as rewards and recognition) with those of others. When employees perceive an imbalance or unfairness, they will take action to restore equity.

Social Exchange Theory (SET) (Blau, 1964)

Blau's (1964) theory posits that organisational conditions encourage employees to reciprocate the benefits they receive. According to Blau, the relationship between employees and organisations is rooted in both social and economic exchanges. This exchange is guided by the norms of reciprocity, as described by Shapiro (2002), which compel individuals to respond positively when they are treated favourably by

others. Employees who demonstrate organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB), such as working extra hours, being loyal to organisational goals, and volunteering for additional tasks, are frequently driven by a sense of reciprocal obligation.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Job Involvement Overview

Hngoi et al. (2023) reviewed 19 studies on job insecurity, job involvement, organisational support, commitment, and positional characteristics, and found inconclusive results regarding the relationship between job involvement and organisational commitment. Also, Chughtai (2019) reported positive correlations between job involvement, job performance ($r = 0.30$, $p < 0.01$), and organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) ($r = 0.43$, $p < 0.01$), with organisational commitment partially mediating these relationships.

Supervisory Support and Job Involvement

Elias and Mittal (2011) found that supervisory support for change initiatives positively influenced job satisfaction and involvement, with job satisfaction mediating the relationship. Okediji et al. (2011) similarly demonstrated that co-worker involvement and supervisory support significantly impacted job satisfaction.

OCB and Job Involvement

Dwirosanti (2017) revealed that transformational leadership, personality, and job involvement positively affected OCB among Indonesian ministry officials. Sukri et al. (2015) found that motivation, OCB, and job satisfaction significantly influenced job involvement among academic staff at UniMAP.

METHODOLOGY

Research design and area

The researcher used a cross-sectional analytical survey design to describe, examine, and interpret variables (at a specific moment) appropriate for the large population studied. Primary data were collected through questionnaires distributed to federal ministries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, while secondary data came from journals, online sources, and textbooks.

Akwa Ibom State, located in Nigeria's South-South zone, covers 7,245,935 square kilometers and is bordered by Rivers, Abia, and Cross River States. Uyo, the capital, serves as the political and administrative center, situated at latitude $5^{\circ}05'$ N and longitude $7^{\circ}50'$ E. The state is rich in natural resources, including petroleum, clay, palm trees, hardwoods, limestone, and natural gas.

Participants

The study population comprised federal civil employees in Uyo, representing twenty-six different ministries, with a total population of 4,416. The participants were senior federal civil servants at level seven and above, aged between 23 and 63 years. From this group, 367 participants were selected, of whom 253 (68.9%) were male and 114 (31.1%) were female. The participants' ages ranged from 23 to 63 years, with a mean age of 40.5 years and a standard deviation of 8.5 years.

Table 1 showing sample of ministries and the percentage of staff that participated in the study

Ministries	Male	Female	Total	Percentage
Min of Education	28	12	40	0.4
Min of Mineral Resources	28	13	41	0.41
Min of Finance	20	13	33	0.33
Min of Justice	33	9	42	0.42
Min of Science and Technology	30	12	42	0.42
Min of Labour and Employment	34	8	42	0.42
Min of Industry and Productivity	28	14	42	0.42
Min of Health	27	18	45	0.45
Min of environment	25	19	44	0.44
Total ministries 9	253	114	367	.367

Measures

The data collection in this study involved the utilisation of the following instruments discussed below:

Job Involvement Scale

Job involvement was assessed using a 20-item Job Involvement Scale (JIS) developed by Lodahl and Kejner (1965). This scale measures the extent to which employees are involved in and attached to their jobs. It uses a 4-point scale, ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Lodahl and Kejner (1965) reported a test-retest reliability coefficient of .90 over a 72-day interval. For Nigerian samples, Mogaji (1997) reported a Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of .80.

Organisational Citizenship Behaviour Scale

The construct was measured using a 16-item Organisational Citizenship Behaviour Scale (OCBS) developed by Lee and Allen (2002) and revalidated for Nigerian samples by Olowookere and Adejuwon (2020). The scale includes two dimensions: Organisational Citizenship Behaviour directed towards individuals (OCBI) and Organisational Citizenship Behaviour directed towards the organisation (OCBO). Each dimension consists of eight items, and the Cronbach's alpha coefficients were

.83 for OCBI, .88 for OCBO, and .86 for the overall scale. Responses were recorded on a 4-point scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree).

Supervisory Support

Supervisory support was assessed using a 15-item Supervisory Support Scale (SSS) developed by Greenhaus, Parasuraman, and Wormley (1990) and revalidated for Nigerian samples by Samuel and Anthony (2022). The scale is rated on a 4-point scale, ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Samuel and Anthony (2022) reported a test-retest reliability coefficient of .93 for this scale. The SSS was used to measure supervisory support among the federal civil service workers.

Procedures and ethical considerations

The study took place at the federal secretariat where staff of the selected federal ministries assisted in the distribution and collection of completed questionnaires using the on-the-spot method. This approach was chosen to ensure efficient use of time and to prevent missing questionnaires. A total of 400 questionnaires were distributed to account for potential attrition and ensure the collection of the required 367 usable responses. Ultimately, all 400 questionnaires were collected, and 367 were found to be usable, resulting in a response rate of 96.6%.

Ethical considerations were paramount, guided by principles such as justice, respect for persons, beneficence, confidentiality, and the non-invasion of privacy, as outlined in the Belmont Report.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics, including percentage and frequency analysis, outlined the demographic profiles of participants. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient assessed relationships among key study variables, evaluating both positive and negative correlations.

For hypothesis testing, multiple linear regression was employed to test the first three hypotheses, enabling a thorough analysis of the proposed relationships and predictions. The analysis utilised version 20 of the statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS).

RESULT

Table 2: Descriptive summary of demographic variables among civil servants in Uyo metropolis

Demographic variables	<i>n</i>	%
Age		
Mean age= 40.49 (SD: 8.47)	367	100
Minimum age = 23		
Maximum age = 61		
Years of Experience		
Mean age= 8.69 (SD: 6.52)	367	100
Minimum age = 0.3 years or 3 months		
Maximum age = 32 years		
Gender		
Male	253	68.9
Female	114	31.1
Total	367	100.
		0

Source: Field Data (2024)

Descriptive results in Table 2 indicates that out of the 367 civil servants investigated, participants' ages ranged from 23 to 61 years, with a mean age of 40.49 years (SD = 8.47). Their years of experience were also examined, revealing a range from 0.3 years to 32 years, with an average of 8.69 years. Regarding gender identity, 253 participants (68.9%) were male, and 114 participants (31.1%) were female.

Table 3: Summary of zero-order correlation showing the correlation of demographic factors and key study variables including job involvement among civil servants

Variables	Age	GR	YOE	SS	OCB	OJ	JI
Age	1						
GR	-.06	1					
YOE	.52**	-.12*	1				
SS	.08	-.12*	-.03	1			
OCB	.04	.04	-.01	.38**	1		
JI	.11**	-.09	.03	.24**	-.03	.06	1

Source: Field data (2024)

*Correlation significant at the 0.01 level and at the 0.05 level

Note: GR = Gender; YOE= Years of Experience; SS= Supervisory Support; OCB= Organisational Citizenship Behaviour; JI= Job Involvement.

As shown in Table 3, a Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationships between all the main study variables, as well as the demographic variables. The analysis revealed that years of working experience (YOE) were positively and moderately correlated with the age of civil servants ($r = .52, p < 0.01$) but negatively correlated with gender ($r = -.12, p < 0.05$). Also, supervisory support was negatively and significantly associated with gender ($r = -.12, p < 0.05$), while it was positively related to organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) ($r = .38, p < 0.01$). Additionally, organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) was positively and significantly related to supervisory support ($r = .56, p < 0.01$) and OCB ($r = .53, p < 0.01$). Lastly, the dependent variable (job involvement), was positively associated with supervisory support ($r = .24, p < 0.01$).

Hypothesis one: Organisational citizenship behaviour will significantly predict job involvement of employees in the federal civil service in Akwa Ibom State.

A multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to test the first hypothesis, as detailed in Table 2. In this analysis, organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) served as the independent variable, and it was found to be a significant predictor of job involvement ($\beta = -.13; t = -2.10; p < 0.05; 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.53, -0.02]$). This result confirms the first hypothesis, which stated that organisational citizenship behaviour would significantly predict job involvement among employees in the federal civil service in Akwa Ibom State.

Hypothesis Two: Supervisory support significantly predicts job involvement among employees in the Federal civil service in Akwa Ibom State.

The multiple linear regression analysis, as shown in Table 3, indicated that supervisory support was a strong predictor ($\beta = .32; t = 5.25; p < 0.05; 95\% \text{ CI } [0.47 - 1.03]$), thereby supporting the hypothesis.

The analysis of the independent variables—organisational justice, organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB), and supervisory support—yielded a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.280, with a multiple correlation determination (R^2) of 0.079, indicating that 7.9% of the variance in job involvement can be attributed to these predictors, with an adjusted R^2 of 0.071. The predictors had a significant joint effect on job involvement ($F(3, 366) = 10.32; p < 0.05$).

On the other hand, stepwise regression analysis revealed that supervisory support was the strongest predictor of job involvement, accounting for 5.8% of the variance, followed by OCB, which accounted for 1.9%.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined job involvement among federal civil service employees in Akwa Ibom State, guided by two research hypotheses.

The first hypothesis which stated that organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) would significantly predict job involvement, a hypothesis that was confirmed. OCB—voluntary behaviours that exceed routine duties—enhances job involvement through intrinsic motivation and commitment to organisational goals (Cem-Ersoy et al., 2015). This finding aligns with Ghonem (2023) and others who observed a positive relationship between OCB and job involvement, autonomy, and empowerment.

The second hypothesis proposed that supervisory support would significantly predict job involvement, which was also confirmed. Increased supervisory support correlates with higher job involvement, reflecting the reciprocal nature of employee interactions in supportive environments. This is consistent with the findings of Uwugiaren and Umemeziam (2020) and Ghasemy et al. (2020). However, it contrasts with Sangkala et al. (2017), who found no significant impact of supervisory support on job clarity among nurses.

Nevertheless, the findings underscore the importance of OCB and supervisory support in fostering job involvement within the federal civil service.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This research underscores the significant roles of organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) and supervisory support in enhancing job involvement among federal civil service employees. From the presentation and analysis carried out, it is submitted that direct relationship exists between supervisory support and job involvement, where higher levels of support are linked to increased engagement, while lower support results in decreased involvement. Additionally, employees exhibiting OCB—behaviours that go beyond their basic job requirements—tend to be more engaged in their work.

To improve job involvement, several key recommendations emerge. First, leaders should enhance supervisory support by fostering an environment that encourages OCB and integrity, while also enforcing effective laws to combat unethical practices and ensure fairness. Second, federal civil service officials need to address employees' material, career, and moral needs by reviewing salaries, incentives, and welfare packages, thereby boosting motivation and productivity.

Promoting organisational justice is also essential. Ensuring fairness in workload distribution and employee treatment can prevent conflicts and foster equity, leading to improved effectiveness. Lastly, involving employees in decision-making processes, especially on matters that affect them, can reduce turnover intentions and enhance commitment, contributing to a positive workplace atmosphere.

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